

Magnetic, Spectral, Thermal and Electrical Properties of New Coordination Polymers

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Coordination polymers of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} with poly-Schiff base derived from 5,5'-methylenebis-(3-nitrosalicylaldehyde) and 1,4-diaminobutane, have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic, spectral and thermal properties. Electrical conductivities of the chelates have been studied.

Transition metal chelates derived from poly-Schiff base have occupied a central position in the development of coordination chemistry of polychelates¹. Recently, poly-Schiff bases have been prepared and their interesting complexation behaviour with metal cations investigated². One of the interesting outcome of these investigations may be the synthesis of several polymeric Schiff bases³.

Here we report the preparation of chelate polymers of bivalent Cu, Ni, Co, Mn and Zn with the Schiff base of 5,5'-methylenebis(3-nitrosalicylaldehyde) with 1,4-diaminobutane. We have also investigated their ir, diffuse reflectance, magnetic and thermogravimetric properties.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of Schiff base (PSB) and their coordination polymers are presented in Table 1. The reaction scheme for the synthesis of polymeric chelates is shown in Scheme 1.

Elemental analysis suggest 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. All the chelates were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents which preclude their characterisation by conventional methods like osmometry, viscometry etc. It was not possible to determine their molar conductances due to their poor solubilities even in DMF.

The polymeric Schiff base shows a medium broad ir band at 3 200–3 600 cm^{-1} assigned⁵ to the phenolic OH stretch. On the other hand, in all the polychelates

Scheme 1

the band appearing in the range 3 240–3 600 cm^{-1} is due to the stretching frequency of the chelated OH group. The ligand exhibits a strong band at 1 630 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$)⁵, and a negative shift by 15–25 cm^{-1} observed in all the polychelates indicates⁶ coordination through nitrogen. The ligand band at 1 290 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}$) is almost unchanged in the polychelates. The ligand band at 1 280 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}-\text{O}$) is found to be unchanged in the polychelates indicating no participation of NO_2 group in coordination⁷.

A study of diffuse reflectance spectra and magnetic

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS DATA AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF POLYCHELATES

Compd. / (Mol. wt of repeat unit, Colour)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	C	H	N	M	
PSB (460.5, Red)	56.8 (57.1)	4.21 (4.7)	13.8 (14.0)	-	-
[Cu-PSB] _n (460.5, Green)	48.9 (49.5)	3.3 (3.6)	12.0 (12.1)	13.2 (13.6)	1.82
[Ni-PSB.2H ₂ O] _n (491.6, Green)	45.9 (46.3)	4.0 (4.27)	10.9 (11.3)	11.2 (11.7)	2.80
[Co-PSB] _n .H ₂ O (474, Brown)	47.8 (48.1)	3.8 (4.0)	11.5 (11.8)	12.2 (12.4)	4.21
[Mn-PSB.2H ₂ O] _n .H ₂ O (506, Brown)	44.7 (45.0)	4.2 (4.54)	10.8 (11.0)	10.7 (10.8)	5.28
[Zn-PSB] _n (462, Yellow)	49.1 (49.3)	3.25 (3.67)	11.8 (12.1)	13.9 (14.0)	Diamag.

PSB = MBNO₂SAL-DAB.

moment provides the most important information about stereochemistry⁸. Dingle⁹ reported a copper complex which is extremely stable and is of planar stereochemistry. Copper complexes of tetradentate Schiff bases were prepared, and the electronic spectra were found to be the subject of a number of investigations for assigning the structure¹⁰. In most cases the Cu^{II} complex possesses only a single broad band, making the assignment of individual electronic transitions difficult. We have observed two bands at 16 370 and 24 310 cm⁻¹ for the Cu^I chelate due to ²B_{1g} → ²A_{2g} transition and charge transfer respectively, indicating planar stereochemistry.

The position of bands at 9 835 (ν_1), 16 390 (ν_2) and 24 510 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) in the Ni^I polychelate indicate a distorted octahedral symmetry¹². These bands can be assigned to the transitions ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F), ³T_{1g}(F) and ³T_{1g}(P) respectively. The general pattern from their spectral data and ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.68) is in agreement with an octahedral symmetry. The Racah's parameter (*B*) was calculated by using the equation¹³,

$$B = \frac{\nu_2 + \nu_3 - 3\nu_1}{15}$$

TABLE 2—ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF LIGAND AND ITS POLYCHELATES

Compound*	σ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	E_a eV
PSB	9.9×10^{13}	0.018
[Cu-PSB] _n	1.71×10^{13}	0.039
[Ni-PSB.2H ₂ O] _n	1.89×10^{11}	0.028
[Co-PSB] _n .H ₂ O	1.25×10^{11}	0.044
[Mn-PSB.2H ₂ O] _n .H ₂ O	1.87×10^{12}	0.092
[Zn-PSB] _n	1.52×10^{11}	0.066

*PSB = MBNO₂SAL-DAB.

Using the value of *B*, an attempt has been made to calculate the transition energies by the relation¹³,

$$\nu_{2,3} = (15B + 30Dq) \pm [(15B - 10Dq)^2 + (12B - 10Dq)]^{1/2}$$

In the Ni^{II} polychelate with an octahedral symmetry, $\nu_1 = 10Dq$ is calculated as $\nu_1 = 10Dq = (\nu_2 + \nu_3) - 5B$.

Various spectral parameters calculated by known method¹⁴ are as follows : for Ni^I complex $Dq = 983.4$, $B = 759.6$, 0.703 , $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.66$; for Co^I complex $Dq = 410.4$, $B = 861.4$, 0.739 , $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.83$.

For the Co^{II} complex, the bands at 8 890, 16 345 and 24 360 cm⁻¹ for transitions ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₂(F), ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁(D) and charge transfer respectively, are probably due to mixing of metal *d* function with ligand functions. The bands are broad and exhibit a great deal of fine structure. The results support tetrahedral geometry¹⁵. The Mn^{II} polychelate exhibits three weak bands at 16 050, 18 970 and 24 900 cm⁻¹ for transitions ⁶A₁(S) → ⁴T_{1g}(G), ⁶A₁(S) → ⁴T_{2g}(G) and ⁶A₁(S) → ⁴A_{1g}, ⁴E_g(G) respectively, at the expected position for an octahedral environment¹⁶.

The magnetic moment of Cu^I polychelate (1.82 B.M.) is slightly higher than the spin-only value of one unpaired electron for square-planar environment¹⁷. The magnetic moment of the Ni^I polychelate (2.80 B.M.) is in the range expected for the spin-only value for the two unpaired electrons in an octahedral or distorted octahedral geometry¹⁸. The magnetic moment of the Co^{II} polychelate (4.21 B.M.) is indicative of a

mixture of low-spin square-planar and high-spin tetrahedral structure¹⁹. The Mn^{II} polychelate shows a magnetic moment of 5.28 B.M. which is in agreement with the spin-only value for an octahedral environment²⁰. The Zn^{II} polychelate is diamagnetic as expected and may have tetrahedral geometry.

Thermal studies of the polymeric metal chelates upon decomposition point indicate that they are thermally stable. Aromatic backbone units are much more stable than the aliphatic one, and they have a significantly higher melting temperature. It is known²¹ that the higher thermal stability of the poly-Schiff bases over the polychelates is due to numerous factors, such as molecular weight, steric effect, and resonance energy along the backbone chain. In the case of the Cu^{II} polymer, the loss of water molecules takes place around 150° and these are considered to be lattice water. On the other hand, in case of the Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} chelates, loss of water molecules is complete at 250° corresponding to coordinated water.

The first systematic investigation of the semiconductor electrolyte interphase in which proper attention was paid to the properties of the semiconductor was that of Brattain and Garrett²². Dewar and Talati²³ also reported on technically useful semiconducting materials. The activation energy and the specific conductivity of the semiconductors were obtained using the relation,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp (E_a/kT)$$

where E_a and σ_0 are the activation energy and the specific conductivity at infinite temperature respectively. The values are given in Table 2. The plots of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ showed that the conductivity of the polychelates is a linear function of the temperature in the studied range.

Experimental

5,5'-Methylenebis(3-nitrosalicylaldehyde), m.p. 198°, was prepared by known method. 1,4-Diaminobutane (Merck) and dioxane were used after distillation.

Synthesis : 1,4-Diaminobutane (1.05 ml, 0.01 mol) JICS-2

and 5,5'-methylenebis(3-nitrosalicylaldehyde) (3.71 g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved separately in alcohol and dioxane and mixed. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h. On cooling, coloured powder (PSB) that separated out was washed with ethanol and dioxane. It was found insoluble in common organic solvents.

The polychelates were obtained by an alternate method²⁴ and all polychelates were found to be insoluble in almost all organic solvents.

All physicochemical measurements were made at room temperature (30°). Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. Diffuse reflectance spectra were measured on a Beckman DK 2A spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer.

The metal content in each coordination polymer was determined by volumetric methods. C, H and N analyses were made on a Coleman analyser.

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